

THE CHANGING SCENARIO OF PRIMARY EDUCATION IN INDIA : A STUDY

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Abstract

My research paper tries to show the impact of upcoming National Education Policy 2020 on the primary school education in India. The whole development of the students is the soul of this policy. It will be implemented from the next year. All the student will be bring in the flow of education. We will find new pedagogical and curricular structure in the education. The foundational, Preparatory, Middle and Secondary are the stages in the school education system. The curriculum of the school is skill based. This is highly structured educational Policy. The Use of Information communication technology is the urgent need in teaching -learning process. So it is included in this policy. According to this educational policy the education system will change and make the students able to compete with foreign students. To impart the quality education to all and to inculcate the constitutional and human values are the aims of this policy. An Innovative teaching approach method will be accepted . This policy is inclusive one .The three language formula will be accepted and the students will be given the choice to select according to him or her. As we know that this policy is inclusive as far as students enrollment is considered. The Students with Disabilities will also become a part of the school and higher education. To teach these students different types of technology will be used by the teachers. It will help to create confidence among them. The age old and classical languages of India will be the part of curriculum. It will be skills oriented education. The different types of skills will be offered along with the school's course of study. Indian education system in this policy is shaped and structured in such a way to the standards of international level. This policy in some way will change the scenario of school education in India . Here the study will be more practical. The education really shapes the future of a country. The scientific and artistic attitude will be developed as well. The doors of knowledge will be open for all.

Key Words: Stages of School Education, Drop out Ratio, Inclusion of all, Three Language Formula, Use of ICT.

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Introduction:

India is a country having rich knowledge and good educational setup. In the times of Ramayana and Mahabharata the students (Princes) were sent to Gurukul for getting education. In the past there were world class universities such as Nalanda and Takshashila in India. In the British rule, British started western education for us. Mahatma Jyotiba Phule and Savitribai Phule started a school in Pune for girls in 1848. They are the real pioneers of education in India. Their contribution is unique .They opened the doors of education for the common people. The Inclusion of all was the prime concern in the education system started by them. According to Swami Vivekananda “Education is the manifestation

of perfection already existing in man.” The National Education Policy 2020 was sanctioned by the union cabinet of India on 29 July 2020. It will be implemented from the next year. It will play an important role in the education system of India. It is prepared taking into consideration of international standards. It came out after the gap of 34years. It is highly practical. The critical approaches are also considered in it. The education is fundamental source to make the future of the country more bright and progressive. The education has completely changed the position of human being. It helps to become man more rational and scientific. The education shapes the future of every country. The education and progress are the two sides of a coin. The National Education Policy 2020 has made modifications in the previous policy of 1986. It has the vision of broadness and more inclusiveness. The Use of ICT in teaching and learning process is one of the major concern of National Education Policy 2020. The Education is a dynamic force require to develop the people in the society .

The previous structure of Education Policy of 1986 that is 10+2 is changed in National Education Policy 2020 as 5+3+3+4. There are different stages in school education such as Foundational, Preparatory, Middle and secondary. The pedagogy and way of teaching are going to change according to National Education Policy 2020. To reduce the burden of books material of small children has considered in this policy. The primary education will be changed. The Students form different socio-economically backgrounds will be brought in the main flow of education. After The Right to Education Act 2009 many children from different castes and religions are brought in the education system. The main focus of this National Education Policy is the inclusion of all. No one should be kept away from the flow of education is one of the objective of this Policy. The holistic development of children will be achieved according to it. In this policy the education will be reached up to the international level. In the primary education the culture of the children will also be the part of teaching. The teachers for teaching in schools will be trained and developed in respect of knowledge and skills. They must have knowledge of ICT tools. Anganwadis will have good infrastructures and trained teachers. The primary education is the backbone of education process. The students of primary schools will have regular health check-ups. The teachers will be trained through educational TV programme and mobile phones. The school education will be spread beyond the obstacles of geographical and social boundaries.

In this National Education Policy 2020 mathematical activities and the student’s abilities such as how to read and write are given more importance. The sustainable development of the every student is discussed. It is the goal of National Education Policy 2020 to attain foundational literacy and numeracy. With the help of technology teachers will be able to teach more interactively. The digital libraries will be set up to help the students for getting books material easily of all class. As far as the health and nutritional level of all students is considered the health cards will be generated to keep the watch on it. It is the aim of this policy to bring back the dropout students in the schools and pre-primary classes. The inclusion of all students including Persons with Disabilities will be focused according to National Education Policy 2020. The distance education will be extended to fulfill the wish of children (students) to get education at home who are not able to go to school due to some reasons.

The practical learning will be promoted. There will be the cross- curricular pedagogical approaches for the complete development of the students. There will be flexibility in course and choice based selection of subjects from arts, humanities and science.

The language is the medium of expression, thoughts, teaching and learning. In the schools onwards the mother tongue of the students will be used as a medium of teaching and learning. One care should be taken not to affect the three

language formula in the school education. The students will have the choice to select at least two languages from the three languages which are native languages of India. The students should be familiar with at least two native languages. We should have proud of our languages and culture which builds the national integration of our country. To attain this thing 'Ek Bharat Shrestha Bharat' programme will be started for the students. The different Indian languages like Sanskrit, Tamil, Telugu, Kannada, Malayalam, Odia, Pali and Persian will be at the choice to offer to students from the language perspective. The students will have also given a chance to select one of the foreign language from Korean, Japanese, Thai, French, German, Spanish, Portuguese and Russian to know the different cultures around the world. The innovative teaching methods will be practiced in language learning as well. The Students will be developed with more modern skills and job oriented works. The ethical, Indian values and constitutional values will be the part of curriculum.

The school textbooks will be changed and based on highly focused upon being constructive. The evaluation of the students work will be more productive and critically based than the previous system. The whole development of students will come to know to his or her parents through the changed format of school progress card. It will be the mirror of student's talent and progressiveness in the learning. The co-curricular exams like Olympiads and other such exams will not only for urban students but for students learning in rural area also. Every student is given an equal chance to develop him or her like the previous National Education Policy of 1986. This is also concerned with students centered approach. The development of student from all sides is the prime objective of this National Education Policy 2020. The Use of ICT and technology in teaching and learning process will be not only considered but also implemented according to this National Education Policy 2020.

The role of teacher in teaching- learning process is the most sacred thing in our country. Since the time of the Ramayana and the Mahabharata teachers has been given more respect in the society. He or she is considered as third Guru after the parent of students. The National Education Policy 2020 has deep impact on school teachers. The female school teachers will be given scholarship for teaching in rural areas especially. The Future teachers need to be qualified TET or NTA to become a teacher. The responsibility of teachers will be only actively participation in teaching process. He or she will not be imposed the burden of other irrelevant works by the system. The works of teachers will be measured and if found excellent will be given incentive to him or her.

The teachers should have the required skills to teach students with disabilities. The initiatives like 'Gender-Inclusion Fund' will be formed by the Government of India to give equal education not only to girls but also to transgender students. In this National Education Policy 2020 we will have the set-up like school complex.

The scenario of primary schools will be change by implementing National Education Policy 2020. We find emphasis on inclusive education for all whether it is cast based, gender discriminated and physical health. The role of teacher in teaching process will also change to meet the needs of the students. The teacher needs to practice of the basic operations of learning tools in this world of the information and communication technological world. The schools will share their innovative ideas with other school under school complex term. We find that many initiatives will be taken by the government to provide quality education in India. The interdisciplinary learning process will be encouraged according to National Education Policy 2020. The constitutional as well as human values will be included in the curriculum and pedagogy. This policy is based on providing unique platform for teaching-learning process. It will broaden the horizons of school education. The students will be more active here. The different stages are considered

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to shape the structure and future of school education in India. It will able the students to think more critically. The Innovative ideas and methods will be implemented as far as teaching and learning process of school education is considered. The student centric approach is more strengthened and highly focused in this policy. We find the creation of interest among the students about the culture and tradition of our country. Here the more emphasis is given on job oriented skills. The easy way of teaching will be accepted to teach difficult subjects like Mathematics, English and Physics. Even a student from science faculty can select the subject from arts faculty. The traditional way of teaching in some way will be replaced by advanced methods.

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